

SOiLO-LiVE

SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY
OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

D7.8

GANTT of annual activities

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Executive Summary

This document contains the different GANTT charts for the implementation of the sustainability protocol and workshops within WP7 (Outreach, dissemination and communications). The GANTT chart shows the schedule of activities carried out with farmers and oil mills for the years 2023, 2024 and the planning for 2025.

These activities include initial audits carried out by Deoleo technicians, external audits carried out by third parties, internal audits to verify compliance and implementation of sustainable practices carried out by Deoleo technicians, characterisation visits to olive groves and visits to olive groves and oil mills to check and help the implementation of sustainable practices.

Finally, the schedule also shows the workshops for farmers held in different municipalities.

4. Activities description

<p>Funded by the European Union</p>	D7.8 – GANTT of Annual Activities
GAP ANALISYS	VERIFICATION OF THE INITIAL STATE OF COMPLIANCE
EXTERNAL AUDIT	THIRD-PARTY AUDITS
INTERNAL AUDIT	AUDITS CARRIED OUT TO INTERNALLY VERIFY THE % OF COMPLIANCE WITH THE MEASURES
VISIT AND CHARACTERIZATION	VISITS MADE BY TECHNICIAN OF DEOLEO TO HELP COOPERATIVES AND AND STUDY THE PLOTS OF THE PARTNERS ADHERED TO THE PROJECT
WORKSHOP	DAYS FOR FARMERS PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES
INTERNAL PREAUDIT	INTERNAL AUDIT PREVIOUS TO THE EXTERNAL

Note: This Proposed Timetable, may vary depending on the availability of farmers and mills